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FOURIER TRANSFORM-INFRARED SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES ON EDIBLE *Punica granatum* FLOWERS

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been designed to analyse Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR) spectrum profile of the edible *Punica granatum* flowers. FT-IR spectrum was done to identify the functional groups of active components based on their peak values in the region of infrared radiation. The results of FT-IR analysis of the present study spectrum revealed the functional constituents such as alkanes, alkynes, amines, alcohol, alkenes, aldehyde and ketone, carboxylic acid, ketone were present in the crude powder of *Punica granatum* flowers. The results of our study generated the FT-IR spectrum profile of edible flowers of *Punica granatum*. The flowers provide opportunities to develop as medicines, value added products and dietary supplements which possess potential health benefits.

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INTRODUCTION

The phytochemicals are the compounds produced by plants manipulated wisely in the pharmacognostic drug development and treatment of the major ailments. The growing need for nutraceutical new foods has generated interest in edible flowers. Edible flowers are receiving renewed interest as rich sources of bioactive compounds [1]. The antioxidant power of the edible flowers is very high when compared to common vegetables and fruits. The pomegranate (*Punica granatum* L.), which belongs to the Punicaceae family, is a nutrient dense food source rich in phytochemical compounds [2, 3]. Pomegranate is an important source of bioactive compounds and different parts of it have been used in medicine for many centuries [4, 5] and the edible parts used pharmaceutically worldwide. The flower has been used as supplement to treat diabetes mellitus in Unani medicine [6].

It is well known that the medicinal compounds comprise hundreds of components, and produce their curative effects through mutual effects with many ingredients, so the limited numbers of specific components cannot reflect the real qualities of the herbal medicines. Therefore, an effective and inexpensive analysis method to entirely monitor the whole constituents of the medicinal materials and their corresponding extract products is required. Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR) has played a vital role in pharmaceutical analysis in recent years. FT-IR spectroscopy is a physico-chemical analytical technique that does not determine concentrations of individual metabolites but provides a snapshot of the metabolic composition of a plant material at a given time. The FT-IR method measures predominantly the vibrations of bonds within chemical functional groups and generates a spectrum that can be regarded as a biochemical or metabolic “fingerprint” of the sample [7].

The FT-IR analysis has proven to be a valuable tool for characterization and identification of compounds or functional groups (chemical bonds) present in an unknown mixture of flower extract [8]. It is a rapid, non-destructive technique with minimum sample preparation necessary [9]. It allows the qualitative determination of organic compounds as the appearance of the bands in the infrared spectrum at a specific frequency, which is further influenced by the surrounding functional groups [10]. Hence, the present study has been designed to study the FT-IR profile of the edible *Punica granatum* flowers.

The main limitation in the use of traditional remedies is the lack of standardization of raw material, manufacturing process and the final product. A biomarker on the other hand is a group of chemical compounds which are in addition to being unique for that plant material also correlates with biological efficacy. So the need arises to lay standards by which the right material could be selected and incorporated into the formulation. However, more work needs to be undertaken to fully characterize these compounds, to identify the active molecules with bioactive roles. To fulfill the requirement, the present study was intended to resolve the functional constituents present in the flowers of *Punica granatum* which will be useful for the proper identification of the active compounds and the chemical profile will be used as a pharmacognostic marker to differentiate the adulterant from the commercial samples. With this knowledge the present study was aimed to identify the functional groups present in crude powder of *Punica granatum* flower through FT-IR spectroscopy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

Fresh flowers of were *Punica granatum* was collected from various parts of Tiruvarur District in the month of December. Procured flowers were washed thoroughly with water to remove earthy matters and made them free from debris. Cleaned flowers were shade dried at room temperature for 10 to 15 days and dried materials were pulverized in mechanical grinder to powder form and passed through a 40 mesh sieve.

FT-IR analysis

FT-IR analysis was performed to detect the characteristic peaks and their functional groups using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer system at the range of 400 to 4000/cm. Peak values for FT-IR were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FTIR relies on the fact that the most molecules absorb light in the infra-red region of the electromagnetic spectrum. This absorption corresponds specifically to the bonds present in the molecule [11]. By using FT-IR, we can confirm the functional constituents present in the plant extract, and identify the medicinal materials from the adulterants and even evaluate the qualities of medicinal materials [12].

Table 1: FT-IR spectrum of edible flowers of *Punica granatum*.

S.No	Peak value frequency cm^{-1}	Bond	Functional group
1	3384.74	N-H stretch	Amines
2	2940.11	CH ₃ , CH ₂ & CH	Alkanes
3	1699.41	C=O stretch	Carboxylic acids
4	1619.41	C-H stretch	Alkanes
5	1446.01	CH ₂ bending	Aldehydes & Ketones
6	1368.73	CH ₃ deformation	Alkanes
7	1191.32	C-N stretch	Amines
8	1077.57	C-N	Amines
9	1058.06	C-O stretch	Alcohols
10	923.75	C-H & =CH ₂	Alkenes

FT-IR: Fourier transform-infrared.

Fig. 1: Fourier transform-infrared spectrum of edible flowers of *Punica granatum*.

The FTIR spectrum was used to identify the functional group of the active components based on the peak value in the region of infrared radiation. The powder of *Punica granatum* flowers was passed into the FTIR and the functional groups of the components were separated based on its peak ratio. The results of *Punica granatum* flower FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of Amines, Alkanes, carboxylic acids, Aldehydes, Ketones, aromatic amines, Alcohols and Alkenes compounds which shows major peaks at 3384.74, 2940.11, 1699.41 cm^{-1} , 1619.49 cm^{-1} , 1446.01 cm^{-1} , 1368.73 cm^{-1} , 1191.32 cm^{-1} , 1077.57, 1058.06 cm^{-1} and 923.75 cm^{-1} respectively (Fig-1; Table- 1).

FT-IR spectrum is a most credible method to validate and identify the mix-substance systems such as traditional medicine and herbal medicine [13]. The results of the present study spectrum also revealed the functional constituents present in the crude powder of *Punica granatum* flowers. Many workers applied the FTIR spectrum as a tool for differentiating, classifying and discriminating closely related plants and other organisms [14].

Therefore, the present work on identification of the functional groups present in *Punica granatum* flowers displayed novel phytochemical markers as useful analytical tool to check not only the quality of the crude flower powder but also to identify the medicinally important edible flowers. Further advanced spectroscopic studies are required for the structural elucidation and identification of bioactive compounds present in the edible *Punica granatum* flowers.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study confirmed that edible flowers of *Punica granatum* are a wealthy resource of phytoconstituents which can be isolated and examined for bio-efficacies and pharmacological activities. The flowers provide opportunities to develop as medicines, value added products and dietary supplements which possess potential health benefits.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors disclose no conflicts of interest for publication of manuscript.

ABBREVIATIONS USED

Abbreviations full term

FT-IR - Fourier transform-infrared

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